

DOES UNIT CELL SIZE PLAY A ROLE? AN OVERVIEW OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOVEN LAMINATES

Mireia Olave¹, Igor Vara¹, Hodei Usabiaga¹, Laurentzi Aretxabaleta², S.V. Lomov³, Dirk Vandepitte⁴

¹IK4-IKERLAN, Arizmendiarieta 2, 20500 Mondragon, Spain
Email: molave@ikerlan.es, web page: <http://www.ikerlan.es>

²Mechanical and Industrial Production Department, Mondragon Unibertsitatea, Mondragón, Spain

³KU Leuven, Dept. of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, Leuven, Belgium

⁴KU Leuven, Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Leuven, Belgium

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ABSTRACT

In this work the unit cell size effect of woven laminates for different mechanical properties is investigated. The selected textile composites are built using the same resin (epoxy), the same fibers (T700) and the same twill woven architecture, but having different yarn size (3K and 12K). The unit cell dimension for 12K is almost 3 times bigger than for 3K while having the same thickness of the laminate. Firstly the internal geometry variability differences are measured. The tensile mechanical properties and the damage are measured afterwards. The mode I and mode II fracture toughness properties are also evaluated. Mode I opening test is performed following the international standard ASTM-D5528 defined for unidirectional (UD) fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites. For Mode II ENF test specimens are selected. Finally fatigue behaviour under mode I is analyzed for each laminate; the mode I fatigue delamination onset and growth are obtained for different woven composites. For almost all measured mechanical properties the results show differences in the behaviour of the woven material depending on the unit cell size.

1 INTRODUCTION

In this research the geometrical and mechanical properties are measured in order to obtain the unit cell scale effect for two woven laminates: internal geometry variability, tensile elastic and strength properties, mode I and mode II fracture toughness values, and fatigue mode I tests are analyzed.

2 MATERIAL

The material is a carbon fibre T700-epoxy reinforced woven laminate made of 2/2 twill woven layers and manufactured from prepreg sheets in an autoclave (for 2 hours, 120°C and 5 bars). Two unit cell dimensions are analysed: 3K (3000 filaments per yarn) and 12K (12000 filaments per yarn) (Figure 1). To obtain a similar thickness value of 3 mm for all laminates, even numbers of layers are applied per material: 14 layers for 3K (total thickness ~ 3.26mm) and 10 layers for 12K (total thickness~ 3.32mm).

Figure 1: Unit cell size for 3K and 12K

3 INTERNAL GEOMETRY VARIABILITY AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

3.1 Internal geometry variability measurements

The cross sections of both materials are observed under an optical camera. The images are analyzed using image manager software of the microscope. Several geometrical parameters are measured: thickness, yarn cross section shape and dimensions, fiber volume fraction, crimp, misalignment of the samples and spacing between yarns [1] (Figure 2). The internal geometry measurements carried out in carbon reinforced woven materials show high scatter values. The internal geometrical variability in the material is higher as the unit cell size increases due to the scale effect. 12K geometrical measurements statistics show a larger scatter for yarn width, thickness and yarn fiber volume fraction than 3K statistics.

Figure 2: Cross sections of 3K and 12K woven materials

3.2 Tensile tests

Tensile tests are done using a standard INSTRON machine (INSTRON 4505) at 1mm/min test speed. The samples are prepared 25 mm width and 135 gauge length, with end tabs made of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite material. Strain measurement is done by strain mapping, which is based on digital image correlation technique (LIMESS). 14 samples are tested for the 3K structure and 9

samples for the 12K. The 12K material shows higher strength/strain than the 3K material (Table 1).

During the tensile tests AE sensors are located at the sample in order to register the acoustic event density and energy levels at each strain value applied on it. For damage analysis after the specimen loading at different strain levels, microscopy and X-radiography are used. For microscopy inspection some samples are removed from the tensile test at a percentage of the final strength value. The microscopic analysis allows us to see the damage at different strain levels and at different locations (inside the width of the specimen and in the edges). For the X-radiography analysis, the loaded specimens are introduced in a penetrant bath for some hours and afterwards they are exposed to soft X-rays to obtain the radiographs.

	12K	3K
Initial modulus [GPa] (Strain: 0-0.1%)	61.54 ± 1.84	68.49 ± 2.9
Modulus [GPa] (Strain 0.1%-0.3%)	65.3 ± 2.6	69.94 ± 2.6
Modulus [GPa] (Strain 0.3%-1%)	66.27 ± 2.06	70.9 ± 3
Strength MPa	1131.93 ± 22.05	959.87 ± 42
Strain %	1.8 ± 0.076	1.45 ± 0.057

Table 1: Mechanical properties from tensile tests

From acoustic emission measurements it is concluded that the 12K material creates more sudden and abrupt changes inside the material than the 3K. The 3K delays the damage initiation respect to the 12K material. In the 12K material there are some matrix-cracks, which can be the reason why it is possible to see the penetrant inside the material during the X-radiography (Figure 3). For the 3K material it is not possible to see any transversal crack using X-ray. This can be because the matrix crack development is generated in the 12K material more easily than in the 3K.

Figure 3: Crack evolution during tensile test for 12K material (at different strain levels)

3.3. Mode I fracture toughness

The delamination damage mechanism in reinforced materials has long been studied because of its big influence on the behaviour and catastrophic failure of the materials. Mode I opening test is performed

following the international standard ASTM-D5528 [2] defined for unidirectional (UD) fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites. A laser device measures the opening displacement and the load is recorded using a load cell. One lateral side of the specimen is painted in white and position marks are defined every 5 mm. Crack front evolution is recorded with a video camera and analysed during the post-process step. The samples are pre-cracked (3 to 5mm) and the crack front location is again defined. The test is carried out with a displacement speed of 3 mm/min and it ends when the crack front reaches 50mm. Eighteen samples per unit cell size are tested.

The opening displacement is applied in a monotonic way. As the material fracture surface geometry is non-homogeneous, load and crack jumps appear during the test; crack front may suddenly increase more than 3-5 mm as the load decreases. From the results it is concluded that fibre bridging effect at the crack front in woven material depends on the unit cell size: bigger unit cell size leads to a higher amount of fibre bridging. Fracture toughness values in mode I for 12K material are double the values for 3K [3] (Table 2).

	3K	12K
Average (J/m ²)	544.67	1100.99
Standard dev.	79.57	127.32
Standard dev. [%]	14.61%	11.56%
Median (J/m ²)	535.75	1106.65

Table 2: Mode I fracture toughness values (18 samples per unit cell size)

3.4. Mode II fracture toughness

Different test configurations are defined for measuring mode II fracture toughness: four point end notch flexure (4ENF), end notch flexure (ENF) or end loaded split test (ELS) are used by different authors [4, 5]. The contribution of the friction, geometric non-linearity and crack tip position measurements are difficult issues to overcome. For this research ENF test specimens are selected. The crack length is evaluated from the compliance values during the test, without visual measurements.

Fifteen samples per material type are measured in this work. The 12K material shows no-stable crack propagation behaviour, appearing jumps of 3-5 mm during the whole test. The 3K material shows more stable crack propagation, almost no crack jump is observed in all tests. For 12K the mode II fracture toughness value is a 16% lower than for 3K (Table 3). The differences on the delaminated surface geometry may be the reason for these differences [6]. During this work the conclusion that the set-up and specimen geometry affects highly the compliance is reached. Attention must be paid in the results when large displacements and high contact angles appear on the supports.

	3K	12K
Average (J/m ²)	3526	3062
Standard deviation (J/m ²)	227	405
Standard deviation [%]	6%	13%
Median (J/m ²)	3493	3006

Table 3: Mode II fracture toughness values (15 samples per unit cell size)

3.5 Mode I fracture toughness under fatigue

The mode I fatigue delamination onset and growth are obtained for the selected woven composites. The standard test method D6115 [7] is defined for measuring fatigue delamination growth onset of UD fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites under mode I. The tests are done in a DCB test set-up

where constant opening amplitude is applied to the samples at different G levels. The tests are carried out at 5 Hz frequency and the R ratio between the minimum and maximum peak displacement is 0.1 (3 – 0.3 mm). Eighteen samples per unit cell size type are measured. From the results it is observed that 3K material presents a higher fatigue delamination threshold value than 12K material (Table 4).

	3K	12K
Fatigue delamination threshold for an infinite life (% of G_{IC})	14.93	6.33
Fatigue delamination threshold for 50% of failure probability at 10^7 cycles (% of G_{IC})	17.33	12.9

Table 4: Fatigue delamination thresholds from ProFatigue software (18 samples per unit cell size)

In order to record the behaviour of crack propagation of the samples (Paris plot), the compliance along the cycles is obtained from the recorded load and displacement data [4, 8]. As previously defined, the frequency is 5Hz and R ratio of 0.1. Fifteen samples per unit cell size are measured. Every N number of cycles the test is stopped and the delamination length is measured. As the DCB test is based on beam theory, a linear relationship between the crack length and the cubic root of the compliance is assumed. From this relationship and the compliance data along the number of cycles the delamination crack length is calculated. Due to the irregular fracture surface, in the Paris plots irregular slopes appear. From the results it is concluded that the unit cell size does not affect the slopes for the Paris plot (Table 5).

	3K	12K
m [-]	7	7.1
Standard dev. [-]	1.4	1.3
Standard dev. [%]	21	19
Median [-]	6.4	6.9

Table 5: Slope value (m) (15 samples per unit cell size)

4 CONCLUSIONS

Different mechanical properties are obtained in this research for two woven unit cell sizes. The internal geometry variability is higher as the unit cell size increases due to the scale effect. The damage during tensile tests is not developed in a similar way for both materials, the 12K material creates more sudden and abrupt changes inside the material than the 3K material. For mode I tests a higher size creates higher fracture toughness values. For mode II the effect is opposite, although the differences are lower. In the Paris plots for mode I fatigue tests the slopes are similar, although threshold values are higher for 3K than for 12K. For almost all mechanical properties the results show differences in the behaviour of the woven material depending on the unit cell size.

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